

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			Title page
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Abstract section
ABSTRACT			Introduction, paragraph 1
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Introduction, end of paragraph 2
INTRODUCTION			Methods, section 2.4 – Inclusion and exclusion criteria
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Methods, section 2.3 – Data sources and search strategy
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Methods, section 2.3 – Search strategy paragraph
METHODS			Methods, section 2.5 – Screening and selection process
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Methods, section 2.7 – Data extraction and thematic synthesis
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Methods, section 2.7 – Data extraction and thematic synthesis
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Methods,

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			section 2.7 – Data extraction and thematic synthesis
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods, section 2.8 – Quality appraisal
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Not applicable – No effect measures used
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Methods, section 2.6 – Analytical framework
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Methods, section 2.7 – Data extraction and thematic synthesis
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Results, Table 2 and Table 3
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Methods, section 2.7 – Data extraction and thematic synthesis
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Not applicable – No heterogeneity analysis
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Not applicable – No

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			sensitivity analysis
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Not applicable – No meta-analysis performed
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Not applicable – No formal certainty assessment
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Results, section 3.1 and Figure 1 – PRISMA Flow Diagram
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Results, section 2.5 – Three excluded articles listed
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Results, Table 2 and Table 3 with citations
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Not applicable – No risk of bias tool applied
RESULTS			Not applicable – No individual study statistics reported
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Results, section 3.4 –

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			Outcomes of CSR in Agriculture
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Not applicable – No statistical synthesis performed
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Not applicable – No heterogeneity analysis
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Not applicable – No sensitivity analysis
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Not applicable – No reporting bias assessment
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Not applicable – No formal GRADE or similar used
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Discussion, section 4 – Conclusion and Implications
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Discussion, paragraph 3
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Methods, section 2.9 – Limitations of the Methodology
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Discussion,

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			final paragraph
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Not registered
DISCUSSION			No protocol prepared
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	No amendments applicable
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Funding section – No funding received
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Disclosure statement – No competing interests declared
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Data availability section – Data available on request
OTHER INFORMATION			Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without

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			meta-analysis.
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Not applicable – This item is not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Not applicable – This item is

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			not relevant for a qualitative SLR without meta-analysis.

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